

Effectiveness Level Analysis and Budget Efficiency at the Regional Financial and Asset Management Agency (BPKAD) Surakarta City in 2019-2021

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Abstract: Regional Government Financial Reports (LKPD) are media for local governments to account for their financial performance to the public. The Regional Government Financial Report (LKPD) is examined annually and receives an assessment in the form of an Opinion from the Financial Supervisory Agency (BPK), when the BPK provides Unqualified Opinion (WTP) on Regional Government Financial Reports. Regional financial management is carried out through a system that is integrated in the cycle of the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBD). The efficiency and effectiveness of the Surakarta city government's financial performance can be calculated and analyzed using ratios and data obtained from the Surakarta city government's Budget Realization Report (LRA), regarding the calculation of the level of effectiveness and efficiency of the 2019-2021 budget realization report. The Surakarta City government for the 2019 and 2021 fiscal years have not yet reached the target but are included in the effective category because they are at the 90%-100 rating, while the efficient level of the Surakarta City government for the 2019-2020 fiscal year is considered capable of saving the spending budget quite well because there are no significant figures. exceed budget

Keywords: Effectiveness, Efficiency, Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget

I. INTRODUCTION

In carrying out Regional Autonomy, Regional Governments are required to run the wheels of government in an effective and efficient manner, so as to be able to encourage the community to play a role in carrying out development and increase equity so that they can develop all the potential possessed by each region. This high demand for performance and accountability for regional performance leads to the need for measuring the performance of local governments so that they are able to build good performance measures [1].

Regional Government Financial Reports (LKPD) are media for local governments to account for their financial performance to the public. The Regional Government Financial Report (LKPD) is examined annually and receives an assessment in the form of an Opinion from the Financial Supervisory Agency (BPK), when the BPK provides Unqualified Opinion (WTP) on Regional Government Financial Statements, it can be said that the financial statements of a local government entity presented and disclosed in a fair and quality manner.

Based on observations by the Surakarta City Government in managing its regional finances, it always gets Unqualified Opinion (WTP) results from the Ministry of Finance (Kemenkeu) for the 11th (eleventh) time in a row since 2010. It is still a record of researchers that even though the Surakarta City Government has received WTP opinion, however, there are still a number of notes that need to be considered by the ranks of the Surakarta City Government, this was conveyed by the BPK of Central Java Province Ayub Amali at the time of handing over the LHP for the Surakarta City LKPD for the 2018 Fiscal Year [2].

Some of these notes relate to Intangible Assets on the Balance Sheet which have not yet been capitalized and the management of Social Assistance Expenditures which, although they have been delivered to beneficiaries, have not been able to be absorbed because they have only been disbursed near the end of the fiscal year. The BPK also found non-compliance with laws and regulations related to the management of BOS funds. This will be studied further related to budget efficiency in the Surakarta City Government for the management of existing funds from the Surakarta City Government.

Thus, the author still needs to pay attention to this phenomenon, so the title of this study is "Analysis Of The Level Of Effectiveness And Efficiency Of The Expenditure Budget In The Regional Financial And Asset Management Agency (BPKAD) IN Surakarta City In 2019-2021".

II. LITERATURE

Local Government Financial Management System

One of the most important elements in the administration of government and development in the regions is the regional financial management system. Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 105 of 2000 concerning regional financial management and accountability states that what is meant by regional finance are all regional rights and obligations in the context of administering regional government which will be valued in money including all forms of regional wealth, within the framework of the Budget. Regional Revenue and Expenditure (APBD). The financial management principles needed to control regional financial policies include:

- a) Accountability;
- b) Value for money;
- c) Honesty in managing public finances;
- d) Transparency;
- e) Control.

Regional Government Financial Reports

Based on Government Regulation Number 71 of 2010 concerning Government Accounting Standards, it states that financial reports are structured reports regarding the financial position and transactions carried out by a reporting entity. The general objective of financial reports is to provide information about the financial position, budget realization, budget surplus, cash flows, results of operations and changes in equity of a reporting entity that is useful for users in making and evaluating decisions regarding the allocation of resources. Presentation of regional financial reports is the presentation of local government financial information that fulfills the 4 qualitative characteristics of financial reports stipulated in Government Regulation Number 71 of 2010.

Budget Realization Report (LRA)

States that the Budget Realization Report is a report that presents an overview of the sources, allocations, and use of financial resources managed by the local government, which describes a comparison between the budget and its realization in one reporting period. Elements that are directly covered by the Budget Realization Report consist of LRA-revenues, spending, transfers, and financing[3].

Regional Revenue and Expenditure Analysis

States that an analysis of regional income and expenditure in general can be seen from the budget realization report. Through budget realization reports, we can carry out income analysis to assess effectiveness and efficiency, the extent to which local governments carry out efficient budgets, avoid unnecessary spending and spend that are not on target[4]. The performance of the regional income and expenditure budget is considered good if the actual spending is lower than the budgeted amount and this shows spending efficiency. In terms of regional spending, it is also important to analyze the harmony of spending because it is related to the function of the budget as a means of distribution, allocation and stability.

Based on information from the expenditure budget realization report, expenditure performance can be analyzed with the following analysis:

- a) Revenue Budget Difference Analysis
Analysis of the difference in the revenue budget is carried out by calculating the difference between the actual revenue budget and the budgeted one. In the analysis of differences in revenue budgets, local governments are said to have good revenue performance if they are able to obtain revenue that exceeds the budgeted amount. Conversely, if the realization of the revenue budget is below the budgeted amount, then it is considered not good.
- b) Analysis of Degrees of Decentralization
Degrees are calculated based on a comparison between the total local revenue and total regional revenue. This ratio shows the degree of contribution of PAD to total regional revenue. The higher the PAD contribution, the higher the local government's ability to carry out decentralization.
- c) Effective Analysis of Regional Original Income

The financial effective ratio of the autonomous region (EKD Ratio) shows the ability of the regional government to realize the planned regional own-source revenue (PAD) compared to the target set based on the real potential of the region. The ability of the region to carry out its duties is categorized as effective if the ratio achieved is at least 1 (100%). However, the higher the ratio effectively describes the ability of the region the better[5].

d) Spending Efficient Analysis

This spending efficiency analysis is used to measure the level of budget savings made by the government. The number resulting from this efficient ratio is not absolute, but relative. We can only say that this year's local government spending is considered to have implemented budget efficiency if the efficiency ratio is less than 100%. Conversely, if it exceeds 100%, it indicates that there has been a waste of the budget.

e) Expenditure Difference Analysis

Expenditure discrepancy analysis is an analysis of differences or discrepancies between actual spending and the budget. Based on the budget realization report presented, it can be seen directly the expenditure variance between the expenditure budget and its realization which can be expressed in terms of nominal value or percentage. Local government performance can be assessed as good if actual spending is less than budgeted, otherwise it indicates poor performance [5].

f) Spending Growth Analysis

Expenditure growth analysis is very useful to determine whether expenditure growth is positive or negative from year to year. In general, spending has a tendency to always go up. The reason for the increase is usually related to inflation adjustments, changes in the rupiah exchange rate, changes in the amount of service coverage and adjustments to macroeconomic factors. Cost growth must be followed by balanced revenue growth.

g) Financing Analysis

Financing analysis can be used to find out the pattern of local government budgets. It can also be used to read local government policies. One of the most urgent items for this financing analysis is the Overtime Budget Calculation (SILPA). The greater the SILPA obtained from a solid budget is used as an indicator of the inaccuracy of presenting a budget plan.

h) Shopping Conformity Analysis

This analysis illustrates how local governments prioritize their optimal allocation of funds. The higher the percentage of funds allocated for spending used to provide facilities and infrastructure, the smaller the portion for the community's economy tends to be.

Effectiveness

Effectiveness according to is a measure to determine success or failure in achieving organizational goals. The regional government budget is categorized as effective if it reaches the target that has been decided. In this effectiveness measurement does not assess the amount of money spent to achieve these goals. However, this effectiveness only assesses whether the targeted goals have been achieved by the government[6].

Efficiency

Efficiency (usability) related to the method of operation. The process of operational activities can be said to be efficient if a product or product uses the lowest possible resources and funds. Efficiency is the ratio between output and input. To measure the level of efficiency in managing finances by looking at the comparison between the realization of the revenue budget and the realization of the expenditure budget. The output is the realization of the budget for obtaining regional revenues and the input is the realization from the local government.

Public Sector Budgeting

According to performance measurement is a method or tool used to record and assess the achievement of implementation of activities based on goals, objectives, and strategies so that organizational progress can be known and improve the quality of decision making and accountability[7]. Public sector performance measurement includes aspects including:

- a) The input group (input) is everything that is needed so that the implementation of activities can run to produce output.
- b) Process group (process) is a measure of activity, both in terms of speed, accuracy, and the level of accuracy in carrying out these activities.
- c) The output group is something that is expected to be achieved directly from an activity that can be tangible or intangible.

- d) The output group (outcome) is everything that reflects the functioning of the activity output in the medium term which has a direct effect.
- e) Group benefits (benefits), namely everything related to the ultimate goal of implementing activities.
- f) The impact group (impact) is the influence that is either positive or negative.

III. METHODOLOGY

The type of research used is descriptive quantitative, namely research which explains existing phenomena by using numbers to obtain an overview and characteristics of the circumstances under study. Research it uses data in the form of a report on Realization of the Revenue and Expenditure Budget Surakarta City Government Area from 2019 to 2021.

Data Collection Techniques

To collect the necessary data and information, the authors use research methods and data collection as follows:

- a) Field research, which is carried out by conducting visits directly to the specified object. In collecting field data, the observation method is used, namely direct observation of the research object by making a concept about the problem related to the author's research title.
- b) Documentation Technique, namely collecting secondary data in the form of data on the realization of the Surakarta City government budget for 2019-2021.

Data Analysis Techniques

The analysis technique used is a quantitative descriptive method. According to quantitative descriptive analysis technique is data analysis by describing or describing the data that has been collected as it is without intending to make general conclusions[8]. Regional government financial report data in the form of budget realization reports obtained, are analyzed using regional financial ratios as follows:

The effective ratio of local own-source revenue is calculated by comparing the realization of PAD revenue with the target of PAD revenue. Regional revenue shows the ability of the region to mobilize PAD revenue according to the target. In assessing the effectiveness of PAD receipts, it can be measured using the formula:

Effective and Efficient Regional Revenue and Expenditure

$$\text{Effectiveness} = \frac{\text{Realization Of PAD Revenue}}{\text{PAD Revenue Target}} \times 100\%$$

Sumber:[5]

Category	Predicate
Very Effective	> 100%
Effective	90% - 100%
Enough Effective	80%-90%
Less Effective	60%-80%
Ineffective	<60%

Sumber : Keputusan Menteri Dalam Negeri No. 690.900-327 Tahun 1996

Spending Efficiency Analysis

This ratio is used to measure the level of budget savings made by the government. Local government budgets can be said to be efficient if the efficiency ratio is less than 100%. Conversely, if it exceeds 100%, there will be a waste of the budget [9]. Spending efficiency can be measured using the formula:

$$\text{Efficiency Ratio} = \frac{\text{Budget Realization}}{\text{Budget}} \times 100\%$$

Sumber: [9]

General Regional Expenditure Efficiency Level Criteria

Category	Predicate
Very Effective	< 60%
Effective	60% - 80%
Enough Effective	80%-90%
Less Effective	90%-100%
Ineffective	>100%

Sumber : Keputusan Menteri Dalam Negeri No. 690.900-327 Tahun 1996

IV. RESULT

Analysis of the Ratio of Effectiveness and Efficiency of the Realization of the Regional Budget of Surakarta City

- a) The calculation of the effectiveness ratio to measure the realization of the Surakarta City revenue budget is:

$$\text{Effectiveness} = \frac{\text{Realization Of PAD Revenue}}{\text{PAD Revenue Target}} \times 100\%$$

Sumber: [9]

Table 1 Criteria for the Effective Level of Regional Original Revenue (PAD)

Category	Predicate
Very Effective	>100%
Effective	90% - 100%
Enough Effective	80%-90%
Less Effective	60%-80%
Ineffective	<60%

Sumber : Keputusan Menteri Dalam Negeri No. 690.900-327 Tahun 1996

- b) The calculation of the efficient ratio to measure the realization of the Surakarta City revenue budget is:

$$\text{Efficiency Ratio} = \frac{\text{Budget Realization}}{\text{Budget}} \times 100\%$$

Sumber: [9]

Table 2 Shopping Efficient Level Criteria

Category	Predicate
Very Effective	< 60%
Effective	60% - 80%
Enough Effective	80%-90%
Less Effective	90%-100%
Ineffective	>100%

Sumber : Keputusan Menteri Dalam Negeri No. 690.900-327 Tahun 1996

Table 3 Summary of Regional Income and Expenditures for the City of Surakarta in 2019

Description	Amount		Difference	
	Budget	Realization	(Rp)	%
1	2	3	4	5
Income	Rp 2.002.535.206.674,00	Rp 1.945.953.241.924,00	Rp 56.581.964.750,00	97,17
Locally-generated revenue	Rp 567.757.960.983,00	Rp 546.020.008.117,00	Rp 21.737.952.866,00	96,17
Transfer Income	Rp 1.383.848.753.473,00	Rp 1.352.907.553.807,00	Rp30.941.199.666,00	97,76
Other Legitimate Income	Rp 50.928.492.218,00	Rp 47.025.680.000,00	Rp 3.902.812.218,00	92,34
Shopping	Rp 2.173.401.766.803,17	Rp 2.011.613.989.386,00	Rp 161.787.777.417,17	92,56
Operations Expenditure	Rp 1.600.943.169.803,17	Rp 1.467.788.487.802,00	Rp 133.154.682.001,17	91,68
Capital Expenditures	Rp 570.458.597.000,00	Rp 543.578.176.920,00	Rp 26.880.420.080,00	95,29
Unexpected Shopping	Rp 2.000.000.000,00	Rp 247.324.664,00	Rp 1.752.675.336,00	12,37

Sumber: Data Diolah Penulis (2022)

Effective Local Revenue

$$\text{Effective Ratio} = \frac{\text{Budget Realization}}{\text{Budget}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Effective Ratio} = \frac{\text{Rp } 1.945.953.241.924}{\text{Rp } 2.002.535.206.674} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Effective Ratio} = 97,17\%$$

Based on the calculation of the effective income ratio above, it shows that the realized budget is smaller than the budget target so that an effective level of 97.17% is achieved. This means that the Surakarta City government is effective in realizing its budget.

Shopping Efficient

$$\text{Spending Efficient Ratio} = \frac{\text{Budget Realization}}{\text{Budget}} \times 100\%$$

- 1)
$$\text{Operations Expenditure} = \frac{\text{Rp } 1.467.788.487.802,00}{\text{Rp } 1.600.943.169.803,17} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Operations Expenditure} = 91,68\%$$
- 2)
$$\text{Capital Expenditures} = \frac{\text{Rp } 543.578.176.920}{\text{Rp } 570.458.597.000} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Capital Expenditures} = 95,29\%$$
- 3)
$$\text{Unexpected Shopping} = \frac{\text{Rp } 247.324.664}{\text{Rp } 2.000.000.000} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Unexpected Shopping} = 12,37\%$$
- 4)
$$\text{Shopping} = \frac{\text{Rp } 2.011.613.989.386,00}{\text{Rp } 2.173.401.766.803,17} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Shopping} = 92,56\%$$

Based on the calculation of the efficient ratio in 2019, it shows that the total efficiency ratio for spending is 92.56%, operating spending is 91.68%, capital spending is 95.29%, unexpected spending is 12.37%. When viewed from the criteria of the Minister of Home Affairs Decree No. 690,900-327 In 1996, operating expenses were classified as less efficient, capital expenditures were classified as less efficient and unexpected expenditures were classified as very efficient. It can be said that the total spending on the Surakarta City government in 2019 shows an achievement percentage of 92.56%, which means it is less efficient.

Table4 Summary of Regional Income and Expenditures for the City of Surakarta in 2020

Description	Amount		Difference	
	Budget	Realization	(Rp)	%
1	2	3	4	5
Income	Rp 1.789.457.852.505,00	Rp 1.831.319.373.387,00	Rp 41.861.520.882,00	102,34
Locally-generated revenue	Rp 402.870.481.279,00	Rp 492.776.208.640	Rp 89.905.727.361,00	112,32
Transfer Income	Rp 1.308.605.395.918,00	Rp 1.269.819.659.567,00	Rp 38.785.736.351,00	97,04
Other Legitimate Income	Rp 77.981.975.308,00	Rp 68.723.505.180,00	Rp 9.258.470.128,00	88,13
Shopping	Rp 1.885.698.744.826,00	Rp 1.638.665.726.421,00	Rp 247.033.018.405,17	86,90
Operations Expenditure	Rp 1.446.695.853.389,00	Rp 1.349.814.240.936,00	Rp 96.881.612.453,00	93,30
Capital Expenditures	Rp 285.769.230.150,00	Rp 250.969.805.187,00	Rp 34.799.424.963,00	87,82
Unexpected Shopping	Rp 153.233.661.287,00	Rp 37.881.680.298,00	Rp 115.351.980.989,00	24,72

Source: Data Processed by Author (2022)

Effective Local Revenue

$$\text{Effective Ratio} = \frac{\text{Budget Realization}}{\text{Budget}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Effective Ratio} = \frac{\text{Rp } 1.831.319.373.387}{\text{Rp } 1.789.457.852.505} \times 100\%$$

Rasio Efektif = 102,34%

Based on the calculation of the effective income ratio above, it shows that the realization of the budget is higher than the budget target so that an effective level of 102.34% is achieved. This means that the Surakarta City government is very effective in realizing its budget.

Expenditure Efficiency

$$\text{Spending Efficient Ratio} = \frac{\text{Budget Realization}}{\text{Budget}} \times 100\%$$

- 1) Operating Expenditures = $\frac{\text{Rp } 1.349.814.240.936}{\text{Rp } 1.446.695.853.389} \times 100\%$
 Operating Expenditures = 93,30%
- 2) Capital Expenditures = $\frac{\text{Rp } 250.969.805.187}{\text{Rp } 285.769.230.150} \times 100\%$
 Capital Expenditures = 87,82%
- 3) Unexpected Shopping = $\frac{\text{Rp } 37.881.680.298}{\text{Rp } 153.233.661.287} \times 100\%$
 Unexpected Shopping = 24,72%

$$4) \text{ Budget} = \frac{\text{Rp } 1.638.665.726.421}{\text{Rp } 1.885.698.744.826} \times 100\% = 86,90\%$$

Based on the calculation of the efficient ratio for 2020, it shows that the total efficiency ratio for spending is 86.90%, operational spending is 93.30%, capital spending is 87.82%, and unexpected spending is 24.72%. When viewed from the criteria of the Minister of Home Affairs Decree No. 690/900-327 In 1996, operating expenses were classified as less efficient, capital expenditures were classified as quite efficient and unexpected expenditures were classified as very efficient. It can be said that the total spending on the Surakarta City government in 2019 shows an achievement percentage of 86.90%, which means it is quite efficient to have increased from the previous year which showed a less efficient percentage.

Table5 Summary of Regional Income and Expenditures for the City of Surakarta in 202

Description	Amount		Difference	
	Budget	Realization	(Rp)	%
1	2	3	4	5
Income	Rp 1.945.769.363.239,46	Rp 1.939.268.856.769,00	Rp 6.500.506.470,46	99,67
Locally-generated revenue	Rp 514.200.704.362,46	Rp 560.579.997.086,00	Rp 46.379.292.723,54	109,02
Transfer Income	Rp 1.370.600.374.312,00	Rp 1.321.146.389.683,00	Rp 49.453.984.629,00	96,39
Other Legitimate Income	Rp 60.968.975.565,00	Rp 57.542.470.000,00	Rp 3.425.814.565,00	94,38
Shopping	Rp 1.885.698.744.826,00	Rp 1.866.496.348.304,00	Rp 320.815.759.793,72	85,33
Operations Expenditure	Rp 1.446.695.853.389,00	Rp 1.489.917.451.913,00	Rp 174.260.038.821,72	89,53
Capital Expenditures	Rp 285.769.230.150,00	Rp 341.100.953.660,00	Rp 72.379.699.703,00	82,50
Unexpected Shopping	Rp 153.233.661.287,00	Rp 35.4223.942.731,00	Rp 74.176.057.269,00	32,32

Source: Data Processed by Author (2022)

Effective Local Revenue

$$\text{Effective Ratio} = \frac{\text{Budget Realization}}{\text{Budget}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Effective Ratio} = \frac{\text{Rp } 1.939.268.856.769,00}{\text{Rp } 1.945.769.363.239,46} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Effective Ratio} = 99,67\%$$

Based on the calculation of the effective income ratio above, it shows that the realization of the budget is higher than the budget target so that an effective level of 99.67% is achieved. This means that the Surakarta City government is effective in realizing its budget.

Expenditure Efficiency

$$\text{Spending Efficient Ratio} = \frac{\text{Budget Realization}}{\text{Budget}} \times 100\%$$

$$1) \text{ Operating Expenditures} = \frac{\text{Rp } 1.489.971.451.913,00}{\text{Rp } 1.664.231.490.734,72} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Operating Expenditures} = 89,53\%$$

$$2) \text{ Capital Expenditures} = \frac{\text{Rp } 341.100.953.660}{\text{Rp } 413.480.653.363} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Capital Expenditures} = 82,50\%$$

$$3) \text{ Unexpected Shopping} = \frac{\text{Rp } 35.423.942.731}{\text{Rp } 109.600.000.000} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Unexpected Shopping} = 32,32\%$$

$$4) \text{ Shopping} = \frac{\text{Rp } 1.866.496.348.304,00}{\text{Rp } 2.187.312.144.097,72} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Shopping} = 85,33\%$$

Based on the calculation of the efficient ratio in 2021, it shows that the total efficiency ratio for spending is 85.33%, operational spending is 89.53%, capital spending is 82.50%, and unexpected spending is 32.32%. When viewed from the criteria of the Minister of Home Affairs Decree No. 690,900-327 In 1996, operational expenditure was classified as quite efficient, capital expenditure was classified as quite efficient and unexpected expenditure was classified as very efficient. It can be said that the total spending on the Surakarta City government in 2019 shows an achievement percentage of 85.33%, which means it is quite efficient to experience an increase in percentage from the previous year.

Table6 Effective Ratio of Surakarta City Revenue Budget FY 2019-2021

Year	Budget	Realization	Percentage	Effective Analysis
2019	Rp 2.002.535.206.674,00	Rp 1.945.953.241.924,00	97,17%	Effective
2020	Rp 1.789.457.852.505,00	Rp 1.831.319.373.387,00	102,34%	Very effective
2021	Rp 1.945.769.363.239,46	Rp 1.939.268.856.769,00	99,67%	Effective

Source: Data Processed by Author (2022)

Based on the table above it is known that the effective ratio of the Surakarta City government's revenue in 2019 was 97.17% and 99.67% in 2021 had not yet reached the target but was included in the effective category in realizing the revenue budget, this was due to the realization of the revenue budget being smaller than the budget target income. Whereas in 2020, 102.34% had exceeded the budget target so that it was included in the very effective category, this was due to the fact that the budget realization was greater than the revenue budget target.

Picture 1Graph of Realization and Revenue Budget of the Surakarta City Government 2019-2021

Based on the revenue budget realization graph above, it shows that the revenue budget realization in 2019 and 2021 is smaller than the budgeted amount, while in 2020 the budget realization is higher than the budget target. In 2019-2020 the budget and revenue realization have decreased, namely in 2019 the revenue budget was IDR 2,002,535,206,647 while the realization was smaller, IDR 1,945,953,241,924 with a percentage of 97.17% and in 2020 the revenue budget was IDR 1,789,457,852,505 while the realization was higher by IDR 1,831,319,373,387 with a percentage of 102.34%, then in 2021 there was an increase in revenue budget of IDR 1,945,769,363,239.46 while a smaller realization was IDR 1,939,268,856,769 with a percentage of 99.67%.

Table 7 Efficient Association of Surakarta City Expenditure Budget FY 2019-2021

Year	Budget	Realization	Percentage	Effective Analysis
2019	Rp 2.173.401.766.803,17	Rp 2.011.613.989.386	92,56%	Less effective
2020	Rp 1.885.698.744.826,00	Rp 1.638.665.726.421	86,90%	Effective enough
2021	Rp 2.187.312.144.097,72	Rp 1.866.496.348.304	85,33%	Effective enough

Source: Data Processed by Author (2022)

Based on the table above, it is known that the percentage of efficient ratio for government spending in Surakarta City in 2019 was 92.56% which was classified as less efficient, while in 2020 it was 86.90% and in 2021 it was 85.33% which was quite efficient. It can be said that the Surakarta City government in those three years was quite good at saving its budget.

Picture2Graph of Realization and Regional Expenditure Budget of Surakarta City Government 2019-2021

Based on the graph of revenue expenditure realization above, it shows that the higher the achievement percentage, the lower the efficiency level. Overall, the realization of spending on the Surakarta City Government has been lower than the budget.

Results of Effectiveness Ratio Analysis

Based on the results of the research on the effective ratio of the revenue budget in the regional government of Surakarta City for the 2019 and 2021 fiscal years it is considered effective, while in 2020 it is considered very effective in managing the revenue budget, namely 97.17%; 102.34%; and 99.67%.

Results of Efficiency Ratio Analysis

Based on the results of the research on the efficiency ratio of spending on the Surakarta City government, it is considered quite good in managing the budget sparingly from 2019 to 2021, this is indicated by the realization of the Surakarta City expenditure budget which does not exceed the expenditure budget. Efficient ratio in using the spending budget The percentage of achievements in 2019 of 92.56% is in the less efficient category. But in 2020 it was 86.90% and in 2021 it was 85.33% which can be said to be quite efficient. So if you do the average percentage of spending achievements over the three years it shows 88.26% or quite efficient.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on research that has been conducted at the Surakarta City Regional Financial and Asset Management Agency (BPKAD) regarding the calculation of the level of effectiveness and efficiency of the 2019-2021 budget realization report, it can be concluded that the effective level of Surakarta City government revenue for the 2019-2021 fiscal year has not yet reached the target but included in the effective category because it is in the predicate of 90% - 100%, this can be seen from the smaller amount of actual revenue budget compared to the targeted budget, namely 97.17% and 99.67%.

The efficient level of the Surakarta City government for the 2019-2020 fiscal year is considered capable of saving the spending budget quite well because there are no figures that exceed the spending budget. It was found that the percentage of achievements in 2019 was 92.56% which can be said to be less efficient.

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